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Review Article

Cheiloscopy- Lip Prints In Forensic Odontology: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Identification connotes “Determination of individuality of a person either alive or dead”. Finger prints, dental data, anthropometry & DNA analysis are the tools used for identification purposes. One of the areas of human identification is Cheiloscopy, the name given to the study of the lips and their unique characteristics. Lip prints like finger prints are distinctive to an individual, and analysis of lip prints is very easy and economical. Recording of lip prints and maintaining ante mortem data can be included as a component in dental records, as it may help in future person recognition. In this modern world of crime and violence, Lip prints can be considered as significant evidence to identify suspects and victims and hence, these prints may be a budding investigative resource in forensic dental science.

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INTRODUCTION:

Human recognition is one of the most challenging subjects that man has been confronted with. Identification is a set of physical characteristics, functional or psychic, and normal or pathological- that describes an individual. Establishment of the personal identification of both the living person and the dead is often necessary for a variety of reasons.² Forensic odontology plays key role in identification of human remains. DNA isolation may be pricey and technique sensitive hence, dental records provide durable evidence in post mortem identification.² Forensic investigation techniques that deals with person identification based on lip prints is called cheiloscropy (derived from the Greek word 'Cheilos' which means lips and 'skopein' means to see).^{1,4}

Cheiloscropy, deals with the recognition of Humans based on Lip traces, is based on the fact that the pattern of lines on the red part of human lips is inimitable for each human being. The wrinkles and grooves on labial mucosa, called as sulci labiorum, forms the

characteristic pattern that are studied while examining lip prints.⁴ Due to the various important functions of the lips like appearance, speech, swallowing, emotional expression, tactile sensation, whistling, blowing and kissing in day to day life, they are one of the important Investigation tool in forensic odontology. Among other latent traces, lip prints or impressions of the human lips can be found at a crime scene. They are often left on objects such as cups, glasses, cigarettes, windows, doors and clothing.³ Lip prints can be recognized as early as sixth week of intrauterine life and remain same during the life of an individual. Even after diseased or pathological condition such as trauma, inflammation and viral infection like Herpes, Lip prints recover and can be recognized without difficulty.⁷ The disposition and form of furrows does not vary with environmental factors. The lip prints of parents and children and those of siblings have shown some similarities.³

Highlights of Cheiloscropy^{1,2,5,7,8}.

Year	Occurrence
1902	The biological phenomenon of systems of furrows on the red part of human lips was first described by Anthropologists- R. Fischer
1932	Lip prints were first recommended as a tool for identification by Edmond Locard- one of France's greatest criminologists
1950	Its use as a method of identification was described in textbooks on homicide investigation.
1961	First research in Europe was carried out on the subject of Lip Prints in Hungary. The examination started when lip traces were found on a glass door at the scene of murder
1966	In Poland, the interest in lip prints started in 1966, when accidentally a lip print was revealed on the window glass at the scene of burglary.
1966	Dr. Martin Santos from Brazil presented his own classification of Lip furrows and lines
1970	Lip prints were classified into different groups.
1968-1971	Two Japanese scientists Yasuo Tsuchihashi and Tazuo Suzuki examined 1364 persons at the department of Forensic Odontology at Tokyo University & established that the arrangement of lines on the red part of human lips is individual and unique for each human being.
1974	Tsuchihashi carried out another study with greater number of participants as well as family groups and add strength to the theory of heredity of lip prints
1981	Cotton reported in his book "Outline of Forensic Dentistry" that cheiloscropy is one of the special techniques used for personal identification
1982	A project was launched in the Forensic Institute of Warsaw University Criminal law department in cooperation with the former Forensic Institute of Milita in Warsaw with the aim of developing one cohesive Cheiloscopic system practicable in forensic cheiloscropy.

1985	The methods of finding and recovery of lip traces, recovering comparative material and the techniques employed to carry out that expertise have been introduced into case work of Fingerprint department of the Central Forensic Laboratory of Police in Warsaw, Poland
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Classification of lip Prints:

On the lips, the Klein’s zone is the mucosal area which is covered with wrinkles and grooves that form the characteristic lip pattern and lip prints.⁷ Different aspects of lip prints were studied like stability, uniqueness, characters on the bases of which sex of a person can be determined on the basis of lip prints and various other morphological characters among different groups of population.^{1,4} Different classification had been given till today for the identification of the lip Prints. They are as follows:

1. Clauco Martin Santos lip print classification

(1967)⁷: Divided the nature of wrinkles and grooves into simple and compound types.

A. Simple type: When they are formed only by one element

- straight line
- curved line
- An angled line
- Sine shaped line

B. Compound type: When they are formed by more than one element.

- Bifurcated
- Trifurcated
- Anomalous

2. Suzuki and Tsuchihashi lip print classification:

(1970)⁷

Figure 1: Suzuki and Tsuchihashi lip print classification

Type I	Clear cut vertical grooves that run across the entire lip.
Type I	Similar to type i but that do not run across the entire lip.

Type II	Branched groove (branched y pattern).
Type III	Intersected grooves
Type IV	Reticular grooves.
Type V	Undetermined

3. Renaud’s Classification: (1973)^{4,5,7}

- A. Complete vertical
- B. Incomplete vertical
- C. Complete Bifurcated
- D. Incomplete Bifurcated
- E. Complete Branched

Figure 2: Renaud’s Classification

- F. Incomplete Branched
- G. Reticular Pattern
- H. X or Coma form
- I. Horizontal
- J. Other forms (Ellipse, Triangle)

4. Afchar – Bayat Classification (1979)^{4,5:}

- A1: Vertical and Straight grooves, covering the whole lip
- A2 : Vertical and Straight grooves, but not covering the whole lip
- B1 : Straight branched grooves
- B2 : Angulated branched grooves
- C : Converging grooves
- D : Reticular pattern grooves
- E : Other grooves.

5. Recently, only a 10mm portion of the middle part of the lower lip is used for the basis of the classification as this fragment is almost visible in any trace. The determination of the pattern depends on the numerical superiority of properties of the lines on the fragment⁷.
- Linear: L
 - Bifurcation: R
 - Reticular: S
 - Undetermined: N

Significance of lip prints:

1. A deterministic aid for forensic sex determination.
2. A tool in crime investigation
3. An aid for personal identification
4. An aid for human recognition
5. Cheiloscropy is significant for legal as well as humanitarian rationales.

Limitations of lip prints:

- The most familiar barrier that is encountered during the study of lip prints is that there is smudging or spoiling of the lip prints which leads to unidentifiable marks that causes interruption in personal identification.^{1,3}
- Any treatment rendered after any major trauma to the lips will cause scarring as a result will alter the pattern of the lips.¹
- It is complicated to decide the pattern of the lip prints when inflammation is present in the lip.⁴
- A major limitation of Cheiloscropy is that in very little circumstances ante mortem data is available to judge against with post-mortem evidence which obviously impairs a comparative study.⁷

CONCLUSION:

Cheiloscropy must be given equal significance and recognition as, it allows us to carry out judicial investigations that guides us towards clearer information, a technique like this must not be ignored but given equal weightage as, it provides data that lays

down the identification and individualization of a suspect.^{2,3} Lip prints like finger prints are exclusive to an individual, and analysis of lip prints is very simple and inexpensive. Recording of lip prints and preserving ante mortem data can be included as a component in dental records, as it may help in future person identification. Lip prints can be considered as key evidence to identify suspects and victims and hence, these prints may be a potential investigative resource in forensic science.

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